

Cite as: Patrick, Gnana. (2007). Development as Quasi-Religious: A Critical Appraisal (Version 1.0). Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies, Jan-June 2007 (10/1), 126-144. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4266861>

Development as Quasi-Religious A Critical Appraisal

Gnana Patrick

Dept of Christianity, University of Madras, Chennai

Abstract: By analysing the idea and practice of development as they emerged during the different phases – such as the enlightenment phase, the post-World War phase, and the present-day globalisation phase, – the essay underlines some of the features of development which make it quasi-religious. It concludes by observing the limitations of the reigning understandings and calls for a critical approach to both development and religion. A broad based approach to development needs to be supported with new forms of religious interventions too. Liberation theology that emerged within Catholic Christianity is one such example of critical intervention of religion in societal transformation. Basing itself on a critical analysis of the structural dimensions of injustice, this theology as a religious intervention rallied the people against oppressors and dominators. This manner of critical religious intervention is a matter of necessity today. Liberation theology must be reinvented. The major religions of the world must give birth to such liberation theologies in order to take on the hegemonic agenda of domination and exploitation couched in the present-day market-led development.

Keywords: Resistance, tyranny of market, Development as Embodiment of Enlightenment Rationality, development as quasi-religious, development and teleology, ethics, conversion, self-negation, broad-based development.

1. Introduction

We are living in an era of market-led development. The Market has become all encompassing, and has even gone to the extent of exercising a ‘tyranny’¹ over the thought and activity of humanity. Development thinking, perhaps, is the most affected. The turn the Doha rounds of talks at WTO in July 2006 took by abandoning the agenda of overall development in favour of creating access for the market is a case in point.²

We find developmental projects undertaken disproportionately. Andhra’s tryst with hi-tech industries is a good example. On the claim of development, Andhra’s ruling elite took the state to the ‘dizzy heights’ of hi-tech development. But the project remained lopsided, and the victims of neglect are the farmers who continue to experience acute frustration (as evident in the cases of suicide). The welfare of those involved in the agricultural sector was sacrificed on the altar of hi-tech development. The huge dams built by throwing the ecosystem out of gear and displacing recklessly the inhabitants of the area of the dam are other examples.

While such experiences of development in a third world country like ours produce moral compunction in our hearts, the so-called ‘developed’ countries are following unethical and questionable means to support their developed status. Production of arms and dumping them on underdeveloped countries, exporting unstable nuclear plants to poorer countries, producing narcotics and smuggling them out to developing countries – are only some examples of the questionable means some countries follow to maintain their developed economy. The news that America produces marijuana as the top cash-crop, more than traditional harvests of wheat, corn, etc is symptomatic!³ That is a window to the kind of dubious practices a recklessly hi-tech developmentally oriented country can involve itself in.

Over against these cases on the ground, a section of developmental theoreticians – postmodern ones – have come to speak about the ‘end of development’.⁴ This manner of speaking goes along with similar discourses as ‘end of history’, ‘end of

the human', 'end of metaphysics', etc that have come to occupy the postmodern discourses. These discourses place a basic mistrust on development, calling it one among the 'metanarratives'. According to them, there is no universal knowledge or pattern of development.

While this apparently is the 'state of affairs' as regards development, it must be stated that it is again only a lopsided representation of the reality of development. Because a vast majority of humanity still remains involved and committed to development. The attempts to eradicate poverty, provide basic amenities, spread education, etc undertaken by sincerely motivated agencies that work among the masses are good examples of the other side of the story of development. Looked at from the 'developing' Indian context, the idea of development and its associated projects still grip the creative dimension of human living. As observed by Rudiger & Heiko, development-theoreticians, "... speaking with people in developing countries, development is still very much alive."⁵

It is against this backdrop of the diverse perceptions of development that this essay intends to look at the interface between religion and development. It makes an appraisal of the question, 'whether development can be treated as a form of religion. If so, in what sense? And, especially from the perspective of the marginalised people, what does it mean to say 'development is analogous to religion or quasi-religious'? This essay does not deal primarily with the question of whether religion impedes or promotes development. This has been discussed for a very long time. Richard Tawney's (*Religion and the Rise of Capitalism*, 1926) or Weber's (*The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism*, 1930) theses are a few of the pioneering answers to such a question. This essay does not primarily concern itself with such a question.

2. Development as an Enlightenment Project

Humanity has experienced several great civilizations. They all have been, in a fundamental sense, the expressions or manifestations of the basic human urge for 'bettering' of human living. By

'bettering' I mean, taking inspiration from Adorno, a 'dialectic' of comparing and confronting 'what *is* with what *could be* or what fits better.'⁶ Bettering of modes of productive activities, patterns of sheltering, dietary systems, systems of social interaction, aesthetic creations, artistic expressions, and so on have been part and parcel of these civilizations. Embedded in them are also concerns for the betterment of 'self' and 'society'. These are but different aspects of the sense of 'bettering'. Such a sense and its associated activities have been, thus, part of human living all along its history.

However, this urge for betterment and the civilizational activities have not been taken to constitute the meaning of what is known presently as 'development'. Development is a modern concept, born during the post-Second World War decades, when the European concern to overcome the impact of devastations and distress ran very high. It was also the period when most of the erstwhile-colonised countries were disentangling themselves from colonial yokes and searching for ways and means of building up their countries. Welfare nation states were the phenomena of this post-colonial era. Several countries became welfare nation-states, and embarked upon a project of state-led development. India, for example, set off on the course of development with the programme of five-year plans. The Green revolution and similar transformations in India owe their origin to the idea of development as conceived by the modern state makers of India.

Though development as a project unfolded during the post-war constructive phase, the roots of the idea lie within the European Enlightenment revolution of the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. The idea got constituted through the combination or configuration of several elements of modernity like social modernisation, industrialisation, urbanisation, enhanced communication technologies and transport facilities, Enlightenment philosophies, etc. Of them, the Enlightenment philosophies of the self and society played an indispensable role in the construction of the idea and practice of development. Enlightenment rationality, for example, was the core element of this development.

2.1. Development as Embodiment of Enlightenment Rationality

The modern concept and practice of development is an embodiment of Enlightenment rationality. Basing itself on such strong foundations as Descartes' *cogito*, which assumed the superiority of the thinking self and Kant's vision of the autonomous agent and instrumental reason, the idea of development has flourished as a modern concept, cultivating the modern self and society. It has incorporated within itself such features of rationality as cause-effect logical reasoning, subject-object scheme, faith in value-neutral objectivity, the unity of the human thinking self, fundamental faith in futuristic progress, etc. Rationality was the defining feature of what came to be known as 'scientific thinking'. The scientific reasoning deployed the instrumental reason to experiment and overpower the forces of nature and matter. Logical positivism, the high product of scientific rationality, came to exert much influence not only in the world of science, but also in social 'development'. Basing on this rationality, theoreticians began to claim with absolute certainty and confidence the course of social evolution, and began to advocate social engineering too. Development became the most favoured child of this positivistic enlightenment rationality.

Enlightenment rationality worked on the basis of a binary of the subject and the object. The subject was a secularly triumphant self that expressed itself in systematic planning and execution of scientific projects. It was a self which had 'freed' itself from, in the words of Kant, 'self-incurred immaturity', i.e. the ability to act on its own, without being guided by an external agent. This self was the autonomous agent, which undertook several scientific rational projects, and 'accomplished' them. Development became, eventually, the site wherein this rational subject actualised itself. The object of the binary was anything external to the self. Nature, the social reality, the emotions, art and culture, – everything became objects of experimentation and utilisation. Human labour too, in and through the process of industrialisation, became objectified and eventually got commoditized.

The autonomy and liberty of the individual are some of the important products of enlightenment thinking. It stressed the importance of the independence of the individual as against any collective that may hold up the individual. The feudal economic system and its attendant consciousness, which stifled the individual, gave way, in the heat of Enlightenment thinking, to capitalist liberal ideas, which ‘freed’ the individual. These liberal ideas impacted upon the economic, political, and social systems. They, in a unique manner, influenced and transformed the religious and ethical systems and behaviours too. The idea and practice of development that arose within this Enlightenment paradigm, with its own specific care of the self and society, began to acquire religious characteristics. In other words, they became quasi-religious.

3. Development as Quasi-Religious

The Enlightenment-tinted interface between development and religion can be analytically explored at different levels. At a very surface level, one can think of religion as providing platforms for developmental activities. It is a fact of history that several religious organisations, structures, and institutions have been involved heart and soul in undertaking developmental projects. These activities aimed at ameliorating or mitigating social evils like poverty, social backwardness, etc. As noted by Rudiger and Heiko, at one phase during the history of development, “development intervention was largely the provision of capital to build up industries, while other aspects of underdevelopment like poverty etc. were left to charitable organisations of the churches, NGOs, etc.”⁷ Thus, by providing a platform for developmental activities, religion interfaced itself with the project of development, but at a very surface level.

A deeper level of interfacing would be the way both exhibited similar characteristics and, in a sense, cross-fertilised each other by playing complementary roles. Exploring this level would mean taking a more philosophical look at the way both these ideas have fecundated each other in relation to historical actualisations. The present essay would like to make some heuristic explorations

on this level and see how development could be understood as a quasi-religious phenomenon.

3.1. The Teleological Element

Teleological thinking, i.e. thinking geared to an end (*telos*) and orienting human potentialities towards achieving that end is one of the anthropological capabilities that distinguishes human beings from others. In the classical metaphysical age, both of the West and East, religions offered the *telos*. Embedding them in mythological language, they presented different eschatological visions as the 'ends' of life, towards which the followers of the respective religions had to orient their lives. These eschatological *telos* were, perhaps, the sources for the emergence of the historical thinking on a unilinear pattern of progress towards a future. In the classical religions, the soul was believed to progress towards the eschatological end. Since religions always linked the attainment of the eschatological future with certain conditional 'preparedness' ('forgiveness of sins' in Christianity) in the present, they also perhaps induced a synchronic moralistic thinking among the religious followers. Thus, in a scheme of faith, the future and the present were linked. This linkage was perhaps the remote origin of the historical thinking that implied a progress towards a future. It can thus be said that unilinear historical progress towards the future, thus emerged out of religious beliefs and behaviours.

During the modern era, the language changed, but the schema remained. Teleological thinking got expressed in secular idioms. Instead of the soul, the self was considered to be progressing along a history. When the human and social sciences were born, they imagined this progression in terms of what is known as *evolution*. Anthropologists thought of progression in terms of human evolution, and social thinkers thought in terms of social ideologies. Socialism, for example, spoke of the *telos* of history as evolving towards the state of socialism.

After the era of ideologies, what fills the vacuum of *telos* thinking is that of development. As noted by Rudiger Korff & Heiko Schrader, "Development ... translates 'reason and

revolution' into 'development'.”⁸ Development, in its unique manner, integrates this teleological thinking. It replaces the old metaphysical comprehension and eschatology with more concrete achievements of the present. And yet, it orients the modern self towards a 'developed' future. As noted by Anton van Harskamp, “it (development) has replaced the idea of a comprehensive, coherent 'grand' narrative of social 'evolution', while at the same time retaining the idea of a linear, progressive advancement apparently necessarily involving all social and living entities.”⁹ As noted by Harskamp again, it may be said that “Development has become a concept – and a moral appeal – functioning as the substitute for the 'old', even old-fashioned, concept of history.”¹⁰ This progressive linear advancement, inherent in development, may be deemed as one of the important elements that make development a quasi-religious phenomenon.

3.2. Unity of the Self

Progress in history implies an agent that is progressing. “Development refers to the idea of a progress that can be applied to nearly *every* social system and *every* social agent, the human self included.”¹¹ The human self, in turn, implies a unity which can progress spatio-temporally. Any development thinking or project, in order to occur, must have an agent who is the source not merely of creativity, but also of continuity. Continuity across time and space, through the endless changes, provides the foundation also for moral responsibility of the act and the actor. All these postulate what is known as 'the unity of the self'.

In this aspect too, it can well be surmised that development functions as a quasi-religious phenomenon. Any religion has at its core a vision of the unified human self. The Upanishadic religion of India speaks of *atman*, Buddhists speak of *jiva*, and Christians speak of the soul. All these are but religious representations of the unified human self. And, this human self progresses towards what is known as the ultimate reality, be it salvation, *mukti*, *nirvana*, etc. What is implied is that the human self provides continuity and responsibility for the actions undertaken by the human beings.

Unity of the self is nurtured by religions also by cultivating a comprehensive vision of life. It combines the past, the present and the future in a religious scheme and presents a religio-moral universe, which serves, in the words of Peter Berger, as the 'sacred canopy'. A 'comprehension' is a must at all levels and in all spheres. By comprehending the external universe, the internal self is also believed to have been comprehended. The Vedic and Upanishadic philosophers saw an external *rta* (regularity) in the cosmos, and transferred it to the internal *atman*. A comprehensive vision of the external world and the unity of the self reinforced each other mutually. And these two elements are shared both by development and religions.

3.3. 'Expansion of the Present'

Govert J. Buijs finds a convergence between religion and development in the manner in which both of them 'expand the present.' According to him, "...religion expands the visible present in order to endow it with the force of non-visible realities... (it) gives 'inspiration': orientation (when choices have to be made), legitimation (when choices are made) and empowerment (to carry on with the choices made). This 'expanded reality' can not be counted mathematically or tested empirically."¹² However, the impact of this is evident in the lives of the practitioners of religions. It serves therapeutically during such negative experiences of life as conflicts and frustrations.

While this is so, Buijs alerts us, religion can also run the risk of alienating human beings from the present:

Religion always runs the risk that the expanded reality not only permeates the present but that it somehow even lets the present almost vanish. The present can be suppressed by the expanded reality. People for example can withdraw themselves into what to the outsider must look like a fantasy-world. Or they act as if the expanded reality is the only thing that counts and become fanatics or even commit violence. So religion does have the inherent risk of making people less attentive to the specific situation they are in.¹³

That being the case with religion, development, in a comparative perspective, functions more moderately and realistically. With its horizontal focus, development thinking and practice expand the present more context-sensitively. The expanded present becomes a site for concrete activities, which in turn, keeps expanding the possibilities of the present in a more gripping manner. Being engaged with the present, thus, is one of the core elements of both religion and development.

3.4. As Applied Ethics

Economics and ethics, in spite of the recent academic interest shown in their inter-relationship,¹⁴ have disparate areas of interest in the conventional understanding of a modern perceiver. While economics is taken to concern itself solely with pure economic growth in terms of production, distribution, consumption, etc, ethics is considered to be a far-away discipline concerned with morality, conscience, will, etc. While this is the apparent understanding, we are able to identify, on the other hand, a strong interest shown in the relationship between ethics and economics right from a very remote past in history. In the Indian context, we have Kautilyar's *Arthashastra* speaking about economics and ethics even during the fourth century B.C. Aristotle and other philosophers of the same era have reflected on the linkage. During the modern era, the father of modern economics, Adam Smith, titled his first book (written in 1759) as *The Theory of Moral Sentiments*. The scholarly connection goes on. But perhaps the linkage has remained primarily at the scholarly level, leaving the masses to guide their economic decisions with their own intuitions.

But it was the discourse and practice of development which combined in a singular manner the scholarly and the practical interests. Both the intelligentsia and the commoner got convinced of the rationale of development and involved themselves in applying the principles of development in their practical living. Development became one of the taken-for-granted assumptions of the common sense of the modern era. This modern concept served as 'applied ethics' in the realm of human conduct. By

providing a vision for the 'development' of the self, it required the individual to discipline his/her activities so that the vision could be achieved. The care of the self along the path of modern education and industry took place under the dictates of development. Development made a moral appeal to involve and commit oneself for the betterment of others too. As observed by Anton van Harskamp, "development is a moral appeal – obviously urging us to help people living in miserable economic and political conditions – as well as a kind of ideology."¹⁵

Development, having become a principle of applied ethics, came closer to the realm of religion. Religions promoted development in their practical guidelines and legitimised it in their theologies. As far as Christianity is concerned, developmental activities became its soul force. In the Indian context, during the post-independence era when the countries involved in building up the nation, Christianity was a trusted partner in the project. Developmental activities were undertaken in the name of social services. Theological anthropological visions, which dwelt upon the progress of the self and society flourished. The whole missionary enterprise, especially of the Protestant missionary movements of the eighteenth-nineteenth centuries, justified their work on the principle of 'civilising mission', a concept quasi-religious in nature. The missionaries of the colonial era thought that God had entrusted them with this task of 'civilising' the people of the colonised countries. A section of the colonial officials too legitimised their colonial presence on the basis of this civilising mission. This mission combined the vision of human development (through education and industry) with the religious calling. We can identify other historical projects of a similar nature. Such endeavours go to underline the relationship religion and development as 'applied ethics' had in history.

3.5. Development as Secular 'Conversion'

A call to conversion demands a transformation 'here and now'. The present moment gets radically detached from the past at the experience of conversion. Religions, especially the missionary

ones, have always stressed this element of conversion. So too development... It challenges the human person to take a decision here and now in favour of a 'bright' future. As perceptively observed by Ufford, "in development, the future is declared to begin *now*. It is opposed to the past and must in fact be 'rescued' from it... The idea of a future severed from the past allows us to see the constitution of development more clearly as a work of hope."¹⁶ It is in these ways development functions as a secular conversion.

It converts the people, almost in a religious mode. Oscar Salemink speaks of the kind of conversion taking place in capitalist development as one of 'religious conversion'. Speaking from his Vietnam situation, he observes that, "this massive *religious conversion* to a creed which sets them apart from the ethnic 'viet' lowlanders sacralises a new lifestyle imposed by the exigencies of capitalist development – austerity, moderation, frugality, thrift, calculus, and individual responsibility – under the auspices of transnational modernity."¹⁷ Development, according to him, is "part and parcel of the multi-dimensional conversion ... along different tracks and ultimately involving a quasi-religious moral conversion to a capitalist ethos as well."¹⁸

Thus, we have seen some of the aspects in which development functions as religion. The religious elements in these aspects play more of a conformist role, supporting rather uncritically the projects undertaken by the development machine – an instrument smeared with the capitalist grease.

4. The 'Achilles Heel'

4.1. The Self-Negation of Enlightenment Development

The Enlightenment development discourse has changed its course. It has taken new attributes of market economy due, as Horkheimer and Adorno would claim, to its own inner self-negating features. The mathematical thinking inherent in development discourse makes it suffer from its self-negation. Mathematical thinking, devoid of all passions, works to reduce the world to mere mathematical formalism, "whose medium is number, the most abstract form of the immediate," and it "holds

thinking firmly to mere immediacy” (246). It means Enlightenment development has been ‘imprisoned’ within the logic and dynamics of self-preservation.

By doing so, it enters into a dialectics of ‘self-negation’ in the sense that even when it builds itself up to preserve it, it empties itself of its own supports. It for example, as noted by Horkheimer and Adorno, “empties itself of all religious and metaphysical sources of value, leaving only power and self-interest as its goals.”¹⁹ Under its grip, human existence sheds its value on its own rights, and acquires value only in terms of what it produces. This self-preserving and self-negating dialectics has led, as a natural result, to the emergence of the market economy. The process started with the beginning of modernity. Descartes’ *cogito* was an important moment of its genesis. Apffel’s observation is pointed:

Decartes’s *cogito* articulates a new style of thought, one disengaged not only from particular social contexts – from the world – but disengaged also from passions. The world is now disenchanted matter, no longer the source of humans’ moral guidance... The emergence of a form of rationality where instrumental control of passions was a constitutive feature was a necessary requirement in the commoditization of labour. The latter development, alongside the commoditization of the other two factors of production, namely land and capital (Polanyi, 1944), was essential to the full-fledged development of a market economy. With the establishment of a market economy, a Cartesian *cogito* harnessed to the pursuit of self-interest deployed itself throughout the public sphere.²⁰

4.2. Globalisation and Development

Led by the Bretton Woods Institutions – WB and IMF – and the WTO, the countries of the world have opened up their markets through structural adjustment programmes during the last quarter of the twentieth century under the project of globalisation. The so-called developed countries were presented as the models of development, and other countries were expected to follow them. As pointed out by Rudiger, “all nations were to follow in the footsteps of the advanced or developed nations, especially the

USA.”²¹ India followed suit during the early nineties, and adopted the structural adjustment programmes. Liberalisation and privatisation have been the sublime policies of these programmes. Through these policies and programmes, markets of different countries have been opened up to MNCs. Correspondingly every economic institution has promoted a culture that places a high premium on consumerism.

Globalisation, the embodiment of market economy, has made development acutely market oriented. It has obtained the shrill voice of extreme commoditization of labour and marketisation of goods. It has left behind the comprehensive vision of human development, in favour of expanding the capitalist market. In accordance with these changes, development has also become a ‘religion of consumerism’ by preaching the ‘gospel of the market’.

4.3. Gospel of the Market – Religion of Consumerism

The market has generated a religion of consumerism today. An exuberant society that delights in consumerist goods celebrates the features of consumerism. It generates an effervescence from out of the consumerist sentiments. And the effervescence and euphoria created by consumerist culture makes it a religion. As observed by Oscar Salemink, the high noon of capitalism that we experience today “thrives on the promise of absolute wealth and the hedonistic fulfilment of desire – the promise of finding paradise in consumption.”²² Oscar’s observation is poignant and pertinent. He continues to say that, “like transcendental religions such as Buddhism or Christianity and like secular religions such as Communism, capitalism requires a project of *quasi-religious, personal conversion* of reverse Weberian type.”²³ Oscar is of the firm opinion that the present capitalist regime, through the ‘gospel of the market’ converts everyone into an ardent consumer. “Development preaches the gospel of the market and holds out the promise of wealth,” and “because we cannot avoid capitalist development, we are all ‘converts’- as consumers and hence producers.”²⁴

The institutions and organisations that speak of development today have come to promote market interests. Political institutions

like the erstwhile Welfare States have vouchsafed to safeguard the interests of the markets. They are no more interested in the welfare of the people. Socio-cultural organisations have come to celebrate it. Bureacracy is geared to clear the impediments. Educational institutions churn out professionals who will fly high the consumerist values. This kind of the shift is well portrayed by Ufford when he says:

The very notion of development as a project of political engagement and responsibility is increasingly seen as anachronistic. Confidence came to be placed in the *market* as a harbinger of development and in the role of free enterprise and free trade in the quest for development. ... This shift to the market is much more encompassing than it seems. It aims at transforming society as a whole into a 'market society'. The metaphor of the market deeply penetrates the conventions of steering, understanding and justifying modes of operation within the non-market sector also, public and private.²⁵

This shift in the focus of development is mediated through the religiosity of consumerism. Everyone is converted to this religion.

5. Broad-basing Development

Development as an Enlightenment project and development as expansion of market forces have serious limitations. The former, as we have seen, is the source of the latter. Both of them are on a continuum as regards the logic of self-preservation, which is at the root of Enlightenment rationality. Concurrent upon these stages of development, there are also corresponding functions of religion. While religion played a status-quoist conformist role during the first phase of development, it tends to play a promotion role favouring market forces during the contemporary phase.

These stages of development and functions of religions, which are dominantly visible, are being critiqued from more broad-based holistic understandings. In the Indian context, the voice of Amartya Sen intones a more holistic understanding. Amartya Sen speaks of development not merely as economic growth in terms of production output and consumption, but as substantive freedom, which he

defines as ‘capability’. By capability he means the multiple capabilities of human beings to have long life, healthy life, ability to interact in the society, ability to be free of social inequalities and domination, ability for participation in political process, etc. Vocalising in favour of a people-centred development that focuses on human agency and social opportunities, Amartya Sen and Jean Dreze state that, “... we cannot interpret economic development merely as expansion in the production of inanimate objects of convenience – the goods and services that are (as Aristotle put it) ‘merely useful and for the sake of something else’. We have to see what these goods and services do to the actual opportunities and freedoms of people, categorized according to class, gender, location, social status, and other relevant distinctions.”²⁶

6. Critical Intervention

This manner of broad-based and critical understanding of development is a matter of necessity today. It is certain that only a broad based participatory development will increase the well-being of individuals and societies, and free them from convulsions. It is also certain that only a critical understanding of development will free the whole project of development from hegemonic agenda of domination. In the words of Ufford, “Development as critical understanding is vital to reconstituting development as a global responsibility, especially as it makes us aware of hegemonic intentions and relationships parading in the name of global solidarity, but itself it is not enough.”²⁷

This new approach of development needs be supported with new forms of religious interventions too. Liberation theology that emerged within Catholic Christianity is one such example of critical intervention of religion in societal transformation. Basing itself on a critical analysis of the structural dimensions of injustice, this theology as a religious intervention rallied the people against oppressors and dominators. This manner of critical religious intervention is a matter of necessity today. Liberation theology must be reinvented. The major religions of the world must give birth to such liberation theologies in order to take on the hegemonic agenda of domination and exploitation couched in the present-day market-led development.

Notes

1. Cf. Pierre Bourdieu, *Acts of Resistance Against the Tyranny of the Market*, New York: The New Press, 1998.
2. Cf. Martin Khor, "Impasse at the WTO: A Development Perspective", *EPW*, Vol. XLI, No. 45, November, 11-17, 2006, pp. 4659-4666.
3. "Marijuana is U.S.' top cash crop", *The Hindu*, Chennai edition, December 21, 2006, p. 20.
4. Cf. Trevor Parfitt, *The End of Development? Modernity, Post-modernity and Development*, London: Pluto Press, 2002.
5. Ruder Korff & Heiko Schrader, "Does the End of Development Revitalise History?", in Ananta Kumar Giri et al., *The Development of Religion – The Religion of Development*, Eburon Delft, 2004, p. 11.
6. *Ibid.*, p. 9.
7. *Ibid.*, p. 12.
8. *Ibid.*
9. Anton Van Harskamp, "Introduction" in Giri, Ananta Kumar, et al. 2004. *The Development of Religion, The Religion of Development*. Eburon Delft, p. 1.
10. *Ibid.*
11. *Ibid.*
12. Govert J. Buijs, "Religion and Development", in Ananta Kumar Giri et al., *The Development of Religion, The Religion of Development*, Eburon Delft, 2004, p. 103.
13. *Ibid.*
14. There is an increasing academic interest shown on the interface on or relationship between economics and ethics today. Scholars are researching on aspects of ethics that contribute to the advancement of economic growth. Cf.
15. Anton Van Harskamp, "Introduction," p. 1.
16. Philip Quarles van Ufford, et al. "Interventions in Development", in *A Moral Critique of Development – In Search of Global Responsibilities*, Routledge, 2003, p. 13.
17. Oscar Salemink, "Development Cooperation as Quasi-Religious Conversion", Ananta Kumar Giri et al., *The Development of Religion, The Religion of Development*, Eburon Delft, 2004, p. 125.

18. *Ibid.*, p. 128.
19. Max Horkheimer and Theodor Adorno, "Dialectic of Enlightenment," in Lawrence E. Cahoon (ed), *From Modernism to Postmodernism: An Anthology*, Blackwell Publishers, p. 243
20. Frederique Apffel-Marglin, "Rationality, the Body, and the World: From Production to Regeneration", in Frederique Apffel-Marglin and Stephen A. Marglin (eds), *Decolonising Knowledge*, Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1996, p. 146.
21. Rudger Korff & Heiko Schrader, "Does the End of Development Revitalise History?", p. 10.
22. Oscar Salemink, p. 126
23. *Ibid.*
24. *Ibid.* p. 129.
25. Philip Quarles van Ufford, et al. "Interventions in Development", p. 5.
26. Jean Dreze and Amartya Sen, *India Development and Participation*, OUP, 2002, p. 3.
27. Philip Quarles van Ufford, p. 17.

Select Bibliography

- Apffel-Marglin, Frederique and Stephen A. Marglin (eds). 1996. *Decolonising Knowledge – From Development to Dialogue*, Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. 1998. *Acts of Resistance Against the Tyranny of the Market*, New York: The New Press.
- Chandavarkar, Anand. 2007. "Economics and Philosophy: Interface and Agenda," *EPW*, Vol. XLII, No. 3, January 20-26, pp. 221-230.
- Cosgel, Metin M. and Lanse Minkler. 2004. "Religious Identity and Consumption," *Review of Social Economy*, vol LXII, No. 3, sep.
- Dreze, Jean and Amartya Sen. 2002. *India Development and Participation*, OUP.
- Giri, Ananta Kumar, et al. 2004. *The Development of Religion, the Religion of Development*. Eburon Delft.
- Giri, Ananta Kumar. 2006. *Reflections and Mobilizations*, SAGE.

- Heelas, Paul (ed). 1998. *Religion, Modernity and Postmodernity*. Blackwell Publishers.
- Horkheimer, Max and Theodor Adorno. 1972. "Dialectic of Enlightenment." Lawrence E. Cahoon (ed), *From Modernism to Postmodernism – An Anthology*, Blackwell publishers, pp. 243-258.
- Mosse, David. 2003. "The making and marketing of participatory development," in Philip Quarles van Ufford, et al., *A Moral Critique of Development – In Search of Global Responsibilities*, Routledge, 2003.
- Parfitt, Trevor. 2002. *The End of Development? Modernity, Postmodernity and Development*, London: Pluto Press.
- Ufford, Philip Quarles van and Ananta Kumar Giri. 2003. *Moral Critique of Development: In Search of Global Responsibilities*. London: Routledge & Eidos.